

MAHALLIY VA UMUMIY ANESTEZYA TA'SIRIDA YURAKDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR

Turniyozov Azamat Asqarovich

Buxoro davlat tibbiyot instituti

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Tajriba hayvonlarida miokarddagi morfologik o'zgarishlarni to'g'ri va aniq tasvirlash patogenezini, tuzilishi va funksiyasidagi o'zgarishlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik mexanizmini tushunish uchun katta ahamiyatga ega. Yurak ko'krak bo'shlig'ida joylashgan bo'lib, deyarli butunlay o'pka bilan o'ralgan va faqat old-pastki sohada erkindir. Yurak urishi va ritmi vegetativ va endokrin tizimlar, gemodinamik omillar [15] tomonidan tartibga solinadi. Yurakni qon bilan ta'minlash chap va o'ng koronar arteriyalar tomonidan amalga oshiriladi; ularda ko'plab tosiqlar yo'q. Chap koronar arteriya chap bo'lmacha va o'pka arteriyasi orasidagi nay ichida intramiokard yo'lidan o'tadi. Kalamushlarda yurakning haqiqiy sirkumfleks arteriyasi yo'q [3].

Yurak fibroblastlari, kardiomiotsitlar, endotelial hujayralar va qon tomir silliq mushak hujayralari yurakning asosiy hujayrali komponentlari hisoblanadi. Sichqonlarning miokardidagi kardiomiotsitlar mahkam o'ralgan parallel to'plamlar shaklida yoki turli yo'nalishdagi to'plamlarda joylashgan. Atriyal kardiomiotsitlar maydoni kichikroq va erkinroq joylashgan. Sichqonlarning miokardlari asosan ikki yadroli kardiomiotsitlar bilan ifodalanadi [11]. Yoshga bog'liq bo'lgan kalamush yuragidagi strukturaviy o'zgarishlar kardiomiotsitlar sonining kamayishi, chap qorincha gipertrofiyasining rivojlanishi va qorincha kameralarining diametrining o'zgarishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Sichqonlarda chap qorincha gipertrofiyasi interstitsial fibrozdan kelib chiqadi [20].

Yurak gipertrofiyasi. Yurakning massasi va hajmining oshishi amiloid cho'kishi, biriktiruvchi to'qimalarning ko'payishi, shish, hujayra elementlari tomonidan infiltratsiya, miotsitlar hajmining oshishi (hajmi, uzunligi va qalinligi, maydoni) bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Kardiomiotsitlar mahalliy yoki diffuz bo'lishi mumkin; Kattalashgan kardiomiotsitlarning sitoplazmasi katta giperxrom yadrolari bilan gipereozinofil bo'lib, ko'pincha miokarddagi fibroz bilan birlashadi [5]. Kardiomiotsitlarning distrofiyasi, apoptozi va nekrozi.

1. Gialin tomchi distrofiyasi - kardiomiotsitlar sitoplazmasida gialinga o'xshash oqsil tomchilari paydo bo'lib, bir-biri bilan qo'shilib, hujayra tanasini to'ldiradi, hujayraning ultrastruktura elementlari esa yo'q qilinadi. Inson miokardida kam uchraydi [11].

2. Gidropik distrofiya - kardiomiotsitlar sitoplazmasida vakuolalar paydo bo'lishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Gialin tomchilari distrofiyasi va gidropik distrofiya ko'pincha sitoplazmaning denaturatsiyasi va koagulyatsiyasi yoki hidratsiyasi va to'qnashuvining ustunligiga qarab sitoplazmatik oqsil almashinuvi buzilishining ketma-ket bosqichlarini ifodalaydi [11]. Katexolaminlarning haddan tashqari dozasi bilan o'tkazilgan tajribalarda kalamushlarning miokardida gialin tomchisi distrofiyasi tashxisi qo'yilgan [13]. Doksorubitsinni kiritish bilan kalamushlarning miokardida gidropik distrofiya qayd etilgan [10]. Kardiomiotsitlarning apoptozi yadroga o'zgarishlar bilan namoyon bo'ladi - xromatin chegarasi (yadroning periferiyasi bo'ylab xromatinning yarim sharlar yoki bo'laklar shaklida kondensatsiyasi), xromatin kondensatsiyasi (yadro piknozi bilan namoyon bo'ladi), yadrolarning notekis konturlari mikronukleuslarga parchalanish bilan lobli ko'rinish); sitoplazmadagi o'zgarishlar - bo'yashning o'zgarishi (erta bosqichda bazofiliya va apoptotik jismlar bosqichida eozinofiliya), vakuolizatsiya (silliq endoplazmatik retikulumning kengayishi tufayli rivojlanadi), kontur va parchalanishning o'zgarishi (hujayrada chuqurliklar va o'simtalar paydo bo'ladi. sirt, undan keyin hujayra parchalanadi) [5]. Efedrin va kofeinni birgalikda qo'llash bilan kalamushlarning miokardida apoptoz va kardiomyositlarning nekrozi aniqlandi [16].

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